

MULTI-IMPACT DAMAGE AND CAI CAPABILITY ON COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper illustrates the hail impact damage and bearing capacity after impact of composite laminates. A numerical model is established for predicting the damage evolution of composites laminates under impact, including multi-impacts and compression after impact. The damage model based continuum damage mechanics(CDMs) is implemented in the ABAQUS Explicit with user subroutine VUMAT. The intralaminar and interlaminar damage and compression after impact(CAI) capacity of specimen was examined in this study. The numerical results of single impact is in good agreement with experiment. With the model proposed, hail multi-impact including dynamic response with damage and compression after impact is investigated. In addition, results for hail impact is compared with traditional steel impact. It is showed that the CAI capacity decreased with the increasing of number of impact for laminates under both hail and steel impact.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates are widely used in various fields, such as automotive, aerospace and wind power industry, over last decades due to their high strength and stiffness to weight ratios. However, composite materials are prone to impact damage caused by foreign object impact loading. Therefore, it is significant to investigate the damage resistance of composite laminate through experimental and numerical methods. For these reasons, a large number of researches have been developed in literatures for impact damage of laminate structure^[1-3].

The multi-impact events, such as hail and debris impact, are also occurs for composite laminates. Currently, there is few studies involving the multi-impact damage of laminate structures^[4]. Furthermore, as a typical multi-impact source of concern, previous study focused on hail impact damage of laminates has been developed^[5, 6]. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the multi-impact damage and bearing capacity after impact on laminates under hail impact.

Finite element method based on continuum damage mechanics (CDMs) is developed recently to cooperate with experimental activity. Composites damage is considered as properties degradation often combined with composites failure criteria^[7]. This approach is considered as a sufficient method to obtain the detailed impact damage on composite structures.

In this paper, a numerical model is established for predicting the damage evolution of composites laminates under single impact and multi-impact. The dynamic response, intra-laminar and inter-laminar damage and CAI are investigated. The damage initiation and evolution of laminates during impact CAI are simulated.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The impact damage of laminates is simulated through ABAQUS/Explicit. The size of panel under hail impact is 300mm×270mm with the thickness of 2.1mm. The panel is modeled by using solid element with eight nodes and each node has three translational degrees of freedom, as shown in Fig1. Clamped boundary condition was applied on the sides of panel.

Figure 1 Finite element model of panel.

In order to present material damage, The strain based 3D Hashin criterion combined with stiffness degradation based on CDMs is implemented through user subroutine VUMAT. It is shown as:

Fiber tension $\varepsilon_{11} > 0$

$$f_{ft} = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{11}}{X_T^\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{12}}{S_{12}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{13}}{S_{13}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Fiber compression $\varepsilon_{11} < 0$

$$f_{fc} = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{11}}{X_C^\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{12}}{S_{12}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{13}}{S_{13}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Matrix tension $\varepsilon_{22} > 0$

$$f_{mt} = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{22}}{Y_T^\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{12}}{S_{12}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{13}}{S_{13}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Matrix compression $\varepsilon_{22} < 0$

$$f_{mc} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{22} E_{22}}{S_{12}^\varepsilon G_{12}}\right)^2 + \frac{\varepsilon_{22}}{Y_C^\varepsilon} \left[\left(\frac{E_{22} Y_C^\varepsilon}{2 G_{12} S_{12}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 - 1 \right] + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{12}}{S_{12}^\varepsilon}\right)^2 \quad (4)$$

After damage initiation, a damage variable resulting in stiffness degradation is introduced to present the damage propagation.

$$d_i(\varepsilon_i) = \frac{\varepsilon_i^f}{\varepsilon_i^f - \varepsilon_i^0} \left(1 - \frac{\varepsilon_i^0}{\varepsilon_i}\right) \quad (5)$$

Hail ice is recognized as isotropic material with perfect elasto-plastic constitutive law with rate dependent. The material parameters are given in Table1.

Table 1 Material parameters of ice hail

Material property value	
Young's modulus E/GPa	9.38
Possion's value ν	0.33
Density /kg m ⁻³	905
Quasi-Static yield strength/MPa	5.3

3 RESULT AND CONCLUSION

3.1 Simulation validation

In order to illustrate the validation of the finite element results, we compare the simulation and experiment of standard specimen under single impact with steel impactor. The result is shown in Fig2.

Figure 2 Comparison of simulation and experiment of the single impact: (a)Contact force history; (b)Deflection history; (c)Damage area

It is indicated that the dynamic response with damage from simulation is almost the same with experimental plot. The shape of delamination of simulation is also similar with that of C-scan. Thus, the finite element model, including material constitutive relation, mesh size and boundary condition, is so rational in this case that the result is reasonable.

3.2 Comparison between steel and ice impactor

To discover the influence of different impactor on the response of typical panel, the impact of steel impactor with diameter of 16mm and ice impactor with diameter of 50mm under impact energy of 215J are investigated. The results are listed in Table 2. The damage initiation time reveals that the damage initiation with ice impactor occurs in the order of matrix tension, delamination, fiber tension, matrix compression and fiber compression, which is different from the steel impactor. The fiber tension happens before the matrix compression for laminate under ice impactor.

Table 2 The initiation time and location of different damage types for typical panel with steel and ice impactor under impact energy of 215J

Impactor	Delamination		Fiber				matrix			
			tension		compression		tension		compression	
	t(ms)	Location	t(ms)	Location	t(ms)	Location	t(ms)	Location	t(ms)	Location
Ice	0.113	I	0.140	B	0.8	I	0.027	B	0.2	I
Steel	0.133	I	0.667	B	1.6	I	0.113	B	0.333	I

3.3 Multi-impact by ice impactor

Multi-impacts of hail ice on a typical panel of aircraft are always found in reality, so it is essential to investigate. The impact location and order are showed in Fig 3(a), and Fig 3(b) and (c) shows the impact results. Fig 3(b) shows the contact force history of during the multi-impact, which indicates the contact force reaches peak value immediately after impact, and the peak value does not change a lot. Fig 3(c) shows the projection of delamination area after every impact, which shows that the delamination damage area increasing along the delamination area edge of last impact. With the increasing of impact times, the damage area increased.

(a) Multi-impact location and order

(b) Contact force history

(c) Delamination area

Figure 3 Multi-impact location and order, and results

3.4 Compression after multi-impact

To evaluate the bear capacity after impact, the compression after impact is also done after every impact during the multi-impact, and the results are shown in Figure 4 and 5.

Fig 4 shows the CAI of steel impactor, it reveals that with the increasing of the impact times, the maximum compression loading after impact decreasing from 78kN to 44kN, which is caused by the increasing of delamination damage after impacts, while the final fracture position and deformation type during compression are similar, as shown in Figure 4. The maximum compression load after multi-impact are showed in Figure 4, which is 78kN, 68kN, 66kN, 52kN and 44kN for one-impact, twice-impact, tri-impact, fourth-impact and fifth impact, respectively. Compared with the specimen without impact, the loading capacity of one-impact, twice-impact, tri-impact, fourth-impact and fifth impact have decreased by 14.3%, 24.8%, 27.8%, 43.0% and 52.1%, individually. The final fracture position is adjacent to the damage location with local buckling.

Figure 4 CAI of Multi-impact and their fiber compression damage in the first layer by steel impactor

Fig 5 shows the CAI of ice impactor, it reveals that with the increasing of the impact times, the maximum compression loading after impact decreasing from 69kN to 35kN, which is caused by the increasing of delamination damage increasing, while the final fracture position and deformation type during compression are similar as shown in Fig 5. The maximum compression load after multi-impact are showed in Figure 5, which is 69kN, 59kN, 46kN, 44kN and 35kN for one-impact, twice-impact, tri-impact, fourth-impact and fifth impact, respectively. Compared with the specimen with one impact, the loading capacity of twice-impact, tri-impact, fourth-impact and fifth impact have decreased by 10%, 30%, 27.8%, 35% and 50%, individually. The final fracture position is adjacent to the damage location with local buckling, which is similar to steel impactor.

Figure 5 CAI of Multi-impact and their fiber compression damage in the first layer by ice impactor

With the proposed model, the comparison of the simulation with experiment of the steel impactor, multi-impacts of hail ice on a typical panel of aircraft is implemented. It is found that:

- 1) The dynamic response of standard specimen with damage from simulation is almost the same with experimental plot. The shape of delamination of simulation is also similar with that of C-scan. The simulation result is reasonable.
- 2) Comparison between steel and ice impactor, the damage initiation with ice impactor occurs in the order of matrix tension, delamination, fiber tension, matrix compression and fiber compression, which is different from the steel impactor. The fiber tension happens before the matrix compression in ice impact.
- 3) Multi-impact by ice impactor: The contact force history of during the multi-impact indicates the contact force reaches peak value immediately after impact, and the peak value does not change a lot. The projection of delamination area after every impact shows that the delamination damage area increases along the delamination area edge of last impact. With the increasing of impact times, the damage area increased.
- 4) The CAI capacity of laminate under steel impact decreases with the increasing of impact time. And the same regulation is found for laminate under ice hail impact. The trend of the CAI capacity of laminates under these two kind of impactor is similar. In addition, the final fracture position is adjacent to the damage location with local buckling.

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